

APPLICATION OF PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS ENHANCING PRODUCTION OF PULSE CROPS: A REVIEW

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Abstract

India ranks first in terms of production and consumption of pulses. Pulses are good source of proteins required for human beings. The consumption of pulses are going to be increased, so there is need to increase the productivity of pulse crop production. To increase the productivity of pulses we have to identify the existing constraints that includes inherent physiological limitations viz., lower germination percentage, indeterminate growth habit, slower dry matter accumulation, decline in nodule activity, photosynthetic characteristics. These limitations are controlled by the application of plant growth regulators (PGR's). Plant growth regulators are familiar to ameliorate the physiological efficiency as well as photosynthetic ability of plants. This paper reviews about application of plant growth regulators (PGR's) to improve these limitations and to increase the yield of pulse crops.

Keywords: Pulse, growth regulators, physiological limitations, yield.

Introduction:

For the production of grains, India has achieved self-sufficiency, but for the production of pulses, it still trails behind. The current availability of grains (430 g/ capita/day) has progressively climbed from 330 g over the last 55 years, whilst the same for pulses has declined from 61 to 32 g (Anonymous, 2007). Increased pulse productivity is vitally needed due to the ever-increasing population pressure that leads to protein deficiency. Pulses play a well-known role in the human diet and in varied farming systems. Pulses are an affordable source of high-quality, lysine-rich protein and a crucial addition to a diet high in cereal. With an average yield of 585 kg ha⁻¹ in 2005–06, India produced 13.1 million tonnes of pulses on 22.4 million hectares (Anonymous, 2007). The cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) stands out among the pulses because its green pods are utilized to make vegetables, while decorticated split grain (dal) is used to make delectable dishes. For milch cattle, cowpea straw is regarded as useful forage. A healthy cowpea crop completely covers the land beneath the "cover crop" and reduces soil erosion and field water loss. Because of this, it is crucial to dryland farming. Because of its 25% protein-rich grains, the cowpea, also known as lobia, is prized for human consumption. It is a significant staple meal in many African countries. The burned seeds are often used as an alternative to coffee. It is also widely grown for feed purposes and is comparable to lucerne in terms of quality. It is used as concentrate feed for cattle as well as for human use. Cowpea grains also comprise 1.8% fat and 60.3% carbs. In Africa, its sensitive leaves and pods are significant food sources. Ethiopia and Sudan. Roasted roots are consumed. The dense canopy helps control weed growth and soil erosion. In savanna locations where it is impossible to cultivate any other crops, cowpea, which can tolerate drought and thrive in poor soils, is an essential crop.

Growth regulators for plants

Chemicals called plant growth regulators are used to change the way plants grow, for example, by promoting branching, reducing shoot growth, enhancing return bloom, removing extra fruit, or changing the maturity of the fruit. PGR performance is influenced by a variety of variables, including the plant's ability to absorb the chemical, the age and vigor of the tree, the dose, the timing, the cultivar, and the weather conditions before, during, and after application. Gibberellins (GA) support seed germination, cell lengthening, shoot growth, and dormancy regulation. The hormone makes the stem elongate. The rosette plants' bolting effect is brought on by the hormone. Many commercial plant roots horticultural products contain NAA, a synthetic plant hormone from the auxin family. For the vegetative multiplication of plants from stem and leaf cuttings, it is a rooting agent. Additionally, plant tissue culture uses it. A sesquiterpene

called abscisic acid plays a crucial function in seed development and maturation, the manufacture of proteins and suitable osmolytes that help plants withstand stresses brought on by biotic or abiotic stimuli, and as a general growth and metabolic activity inhibitor. Gibberellins, cytokinins, auxins, ethylenes, and abscisic acid are examples of traditional plant hormones and growth regulators. Salicylates, polyamines, jasmonates, sterols, oligosaccharides, brassinosteroids, turgorins, systemins, etc. are growth agents with phytohormonal properties.

Plant Growth Regulators' Function

In order to increase productivity, plant growth regulators play an increasingly important role in agriculture summarized in Table 1. According to Khan et al. (2003), salicylic acid is an endogenous growth regulator that controls physiological processes in plants like stomata closure, ion uptake, transpiration, and stress tolerance. Gibberellin, also known as gibberellic acid, is frequently sold as GA3. In general, gibberellin promotes cell growth and division. By breaking dormancy, gibberellic acid. According to Kalyanakar et al. (2008), the use of GA3 can change the morphological and yield features of soybeans. Organic compounds called auxins encourage apical dominance. Cell division and root development are two of auxin's key roles. In numerous leguminous crops, including cow pea (*Vigna unguiculata*) (Mohandoss and Rajesh, 2003), black gram (*Vigna mungo*), and mung bean (*Vigna radiata*), the favorable effects of growth regulators have been explored. When used as foliar sprays at the right growth stage and in the right quantities, these growth regulators have been shown to significantly increase crop output and quality in a variety of field crops (Nagasbramaniam, Pathmanabhan, and Mallika, 2007). According to Ramesh and Thirumuguran (2001), spraying several plant growth regulators may to some extent lessen the flower and fruit drop. substantiate the claim that the proper application of PGRs in food legumes can improve production and quality indices. Abscisic acid (ABA) and gibberellic acid (GA3) combinations are applied to long-day plants to encourage the beginning of floral buds and flowering (Kamuro et al., 1997; 2009). The quality and productivity of legumes are enhanced by phenolic compounds' regulatory function in inhibiting blossom and pod shedding (Awasthi et al. 1997). Growth hormones play a role in the beginning and growth of floral buds in short-day plants (Wain and Taylor, 1965). According to Reese et al. (1995), cytokinin controls the development of the soybean flower and pod. According to Khalil and Mandurah (1989), auxins can enhance the number of leaves per plant, plant height, and seed output in cowpea. According to Upadhyay and Ranjan (2015), soybeans were treated with GA3 (20 ppm) to boost biological yield, seed yield, and

harvesting index. A natural plant hormone called salicylic acid is crucial for a plant's ability to withstand environmental challenges like heat, salt, and drought (El-Tayeb, 2005). According to Maity and Bera (2009), salicylic acid applied topically to green gram affects a variety of biochemical and physiological properties. According to Kamlesh et al. (2017), foliar spraying with brassinolide at 1.0 ppm greatly boosted grain production and biological yield in saline environments. Therefore, research into the impact of growth regulators on the development of pulse crops was considered.

Discussion

The productivity of many crop plants is increased by the widespread usage of plant growth regulators. Exogenous growth regulators can be used to modify a plant's growth, which is typically regulated by naturally occurring growth regulators. Growth regulator application raises crop output potential and product quality in a number of crops. Khatun et al. (2016) demonstrated a substantial impact of plant growth regulators on the number of soybean seed pods per plant, seed pod weight per seed, stover yield per seed, biological yield per seed, moisture content per seed, and seed protein content. Aspirin produced a lot of seed pods, small seeds, seeds with a high protein content, and seeds with a low moisture content (1.60, 19.47, 44.56, and 12.91, respectively).

According to Devi et al. (2011), plants treated with cycocel @ 500 ppm had the highest levels of carotenoids and chlorophyll. According to Bora and Sharma's calculations, a suitable application of Cycocel and GA3 will increase pea seed output and protein content. Shah and Prathapsenan (2008) discovered that the application of CCC @ 1000 ppm increased the number of pods per plant, the number of seeds per pod, and the plant's overall seed yield. In cowpea plants, CCC (300, 400, and 500 ppm), NAA (15, 30, and 45 ppm), and 2,4-D (2 ppm) increased pod length, pod weight, pod number per plant, and seed output, according to Resmi and Gopalkrishnan (2004). According to Prakash et al. (2003), a drop in plant height and an increase in

Conclusion

According to this review paper, plant growth regulators are crucial to the growth and development of pulse crops. Growth regulators help pulse crops become more productive by addressing physiological constraints. Application of growth regulators improves the source-sink relationship. It is important to raise awareness of the benefits of plant growth regulators and to make sure they are widely available. The physiological constraints are affected by plant growth regulators, which also increase pulse productivity. Growth regulators that improve germination parameters include brassinolide and gibberellic acid. Application of spermine, kinetin, delays blooming and pod abscission. IAA and other growth regulators guarantee robust nodule activity in pulses. Greater yield and dry matter partitioning in pulses are guaranteed by NAA.

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Table 1. Plant Growth Regulators' Function

Crop	Dosage and stage of use for crop chemicals	Findings
Greengram	2.0 percent diammonium phosphate plus 40 ppm of naphthalene acetic acid, 0.2 percent boron, and 0.05 percent molybdenum 30 days after sowing	Greater harvest plant height (32.27)
Blackgram	Ten days after the initial spray, at 25 days after sowing, 2.0 percent urea and 1 ppm brassinollide were applied.	The leaf area index was higher (0.34, 0.82, 1.89, and 1.65) during the vegetative and flowering periods. higher crop, leaf area length (60.45 days), and leaf area index (4.18).
Blackgram	40 ppm naphthalene acetic acid + 0.5 percent chelated micro nutrient at 30 and 50 days after sowing	With a total greater dry matter output of 15.98 g plant ⁻¹ and a growth rate of 0.19 g m ⁻² /day.
mungbean	2.0 per cent urea at flowering and pod initiation stage	Higher leaf area (520.83 cm ² /plant)
Blackgram	At the vegetative and flowering stages, apply 2.0% diammonium phosphate + 100 ppm salicylic acid + 0.05% sodium molybdate.	Higher grain output (928 kg ha ⁻¹), haulm yield (1230 kg ha ⁻¹), and pods per plant (34).